

CRITICAL ANALYSIS ON THE MANAGEMENT OF THE MEDICAL SERVICE IN THE ROMANIAN HEALTH SYSTEM, IN THE CONTEXT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

Purpose – *The aim of this paper is to establish the degree of knowledge and subjective perception of responsible factors regarding integrated health care and its value depending on the result, in response to the management of the medical service to the challenges of health crises, in particular the COVID-19 pandemic.*

Methodology/approach – *Proposed hypotheses: 1. The management of the medical service, applied in the management of the crisis triggered by the COVID-19 infection is considered to be adequate to the particular conditions of our health system; 2. The degree of knowledge and perception regarding integrated healthcare and its value depending on the result is insufficient to be able to become a benchmark in the organization of the medical service. We build an interview consisting of thirteen questions, which was applied to ten leading factors responsible for healthcare management: - at the level of health policy - a senator physician, member of the Health Commission of the Senate; - at the level of public administration in the field of quality management in health - an ANMCS evaluator; - at the level of local authority - a deputy executive director, DSP; -at the level of hospital administrators / managers - two medical directors, specialists, County Clinical Hospital and Municipal Clinical Hospital; a Municipal Clinical Hospital manager; two chief physicians of the Service for the Prevention of Infections Associated with Health Care (former medical directors), County Clinical Hospital and Municipal Clinical Hospital; a financial-accounting director of the County Clinical Hospital; - at the level of a higher education medical institution - (from two faculties of Medicine and Pharmacy): a university professor, dean, and an associate professor; The individual interviews were conducted online and recorded over approximately four weeks.*

Findings - *There was interest from the participants, as evidenced by the length of the interviews and the new issues mentioned in the responses. The response rate was one hundred percent. Most participants freely expressed their opinions, bringing arguments. According to the majority answers, the first hypothesis has been confirmed, the other requires further research.*

Research limitations / implications - *1. Qualitative research is based on the subjective interpretation of the author, admitting a margin of error in the objectivity of data analysis. 2. The different opinions of the subjects on the studied aspects do not allow the generalization of some conclusions that may or may not support the theory of integrated medical care and the value of the medical service appreciated according to the result in the patient's health condition.*

Practical implications - *Extensive answers, with nuances or certain clarifications, highlight important details and reveal subtle aspects, obtaining new observations that offer a wider openness to the topic studied and help create a better-defined spectrum to continue with a quantitative research in order to define the conclusions.*

Originality / value - *The dialogue with factors responsible for formulating and applying the management of the medical service at different structural levels, belonging to different institutions, from different regions (Mureș, Dolj, Olt), takes us out of the homogeneity of a group and provides deeper information, with the possibility of confronting them.*

Addressing the subject of value in the medical service in the context of the pandemic crisis provides a real ground for verifying the solution proposed by the theory.

Getting a synthesis of opinions related to specific researched aspects, which is missing from the national literature, develops the possibility of interpreting in a new way the theory under study.

Key words: *integrated medical care, the value represented in the result obtained in the patient's health, the management of the medical service.*

Introduction

In December 2019, the WHO was informed of the appearance of a new coronavirus in the Wuhan community, China, called SARS-CoV-2, which, in a few weeks, would become a "global virus" infecting the whole world with exaggerated speed.

We can consider this event an additional evidence of the relationship between globalization and health or, more precisely, the consequence of political-economic and social ties that transcend national boundaries and affect the health of the population in areas of the world quite distant from each other. COVID-19 infection demonstrates how globalization has spread negative health determinants around the world, significantly increasing risk factors and disease worldwide. Social and health media around the world are experiencing the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, calling into question the sustainability of these systems.

Once again, global healthcare organizations are under pressure to demonstrate how value can be added to healthcare through the activities they carry out.

Without claiming to be the antidote to COVID 19 infection, or to any other pathology, the value-based healthcare model [Porter, 2006], on the other hand, offers added value to the patient, even in situations caused by the unexpected appearance of an extremely contagious and serious infections. Even if it involves a strategic reorientation of medical services, with many changes or changes involved, the new management means progress in developing a system that was created for the needs of the patient and which, unfortunately, as it developed and modernized has acquired characteristics of industry, with economic objectives and purposes, above human ones.

Value-based healthcare benchmarks used in the comparative analysis of COVID-19 infection management

The challenges generated by an extremely serious infection, spread as an effect of globalization, highlight the need to change the management of healthcare, so that it responds to the needs in the medical system related to the pathology of the infected patient.

Designing a management of the medical service, based on integrated medical care, which aims to fully cover the pathological needs of the patient, aiming to improve the outcome of the patient's health and to try first to prevent the disease and then to rehabilitate and to monitor the treated patient, is a value-creating strategy in the medical service even in the conditions of the unexpected appearance of an unknown disease.

Changing the current orientation of medical service management, from a process-based one, in which attention is directed to diagnosing and treating the disease, to a patient-based one, in which attention is directed to the treated person, becomes a new form of approach, known under the name of "value-based healthcare". The new healthcare model [Porter, Teisberg, 2006] does not replace the medical protocol, but provides a new framework for action that remains valid even in the absence of a protocol. The value created by this new management model is obtained by the multidisciplinary approach of the patient's pathology, depending on the particular needs of each and by providing a complete cycle of medical care that includes the chain action of prevention, diagnosis, treatment / intervention, recovery, and monitoring. It also proposes the analysis of the value of the medical service according to the result obtained in the patient's health condition and according to this result the payment of the service. Essential aspects regarding this theory have been detailed in previous articles [Dorobanțu, Marian, 2018, 2019]. The theory developed by Porter and Teisberg ensures the creation of added value in the conditions in which MBD delays in issuing solutions.

Analysis of healthcare management in the context of the crisis generated by COVID-19 infection, in view of the factors responsible

Each of these components of value-based health care, mentioned above, was transposed into at least two questions in an interview to verify its validity in the real context created in the social and health environment by COVID-19 infection.

The first question concerns the challenges faced by healthcare institutions in the face of the unexpected onset of COVID-19 infection.

Even if they were mentioned in a different order by the subjects, the opinions were analyzed according to their weight in the response.

9 of the 10 responses clearly mention the lack of equipment for laboratory tests, protective equipment and medicines and the difficulty of identifying suppliers on the market. Another challenge identified by most respondents refers to the lack of a legislative framework necessary to manage the situation, which was reflected in the gaps between information and decisions, unpredictability of actions and frequent changes of orders issued (from one hour to another), delay in coordinating actions, the bureaucracy of controls. At the highest level there was the issue of designating the institutions to handle this situation and designating the support institutions.

8 out of 10 respondents also emphasize the reorganization of hospital management (triage, functional circuits, provision of buffer zones, isolation zones) as a major challenge, to which is added the lack of new legislation for the operation of hospital wards dedicated to health care for non-covid patients. The shift of all attention (including funding) to healthcare for infected patients has led to the disruption or suppression of routine medical activities.

Also, most of the subjects point out the lack of medical and auxiliary staff and their lack of training to deal with such an epidemic (from the use of protective equipment, control and control of fear, mental balance, to medical activity in the absence of scientific information about the disease).

It is worth mentioning the opinion on the impossibility of moral support of the patient from the medical staff or the family.

Conclusion: The answers show that the Romanian health system, structural and functional, needs a profound reform, an organizational management that will allow it to react promptly in any critical situation, well-intentioned and prepared management staff. There is a lack of information and training of medical staff to be able to respond to critical situations.

It is necessary to establish an electronic information program and a basic training program to respond to the challenges posed by unexpected situations.

The second question concerns healthcare management dedicated to addressing COVID-19 infection, in the absence of a specific evidence-based protocol.

Most respondents agree that the care provided was based on the experience of the medical staff and then on the information coming, quite quickly, from units that had previously tested a certain protocol. However, the answers are focused on the methods of diagnosis, treatment and isolation of patients. An interesting answer expresses the idea that the favorable or unfavorable evolution of the treated patient is not due to the lack of a protocol. Two of the answers consider that the recent increase in the number of cases is not a consequence of management, but a problem of community transmission. There is also a critical view, which expresses confusion and disorganization in healthcare ("chaotic").

Conclusion: The answers expose the confusion that exists regarding the understanding of the concept of healthcare management.

It is necessary to clearly define the management of healthcare and its understanding by those involved in this management. Healthcare providers need to develop a different view of control, responsibility, risk, and outcome in addressing the care they provide to a patient.

Question number three tries to find out the opinion of the interviewees about covering the integral needs of the patient with COVID-19, following the use of loan protocols. Opinions are contradictory.

Some of the interviewees claim that the protocols used covered the patient's needs, although there were adjustments to them as the process progressed. Another party claims that the protocols used had many neuralgic points, referring to the lack of medication, lack of patient counseling or problems related to the method of diagnosis and then treatment for comorbidities. Discontinuities were also found, albeit short-lived, between the time of communication of the validity of a protocol and its application or supply of medicines.

A different answer, determined by the nature of the medical specialty, highlights the rapid local elaboration of operational procedures, before the issuance of official orders regarding the methods, by the higher bodies.

Only one interviewee noticed the lack of a holistic approach of the hospitalized patient with COVID-19, regardless of the protocol used.

Conclusion: These different opinions, somewhat normal, show that the medicine practiced is based on guidelines and protocols, and their lack can lead to confusion or delays in treating the patient. In general, physicians involved in diagnostic and treatment activities are tempted to follow the provisions of the protocols and instructions in the guidelines, rather than creating value for the patient.

The medicine practiced considers the treatment of the disease and less the treatment of the patient. Insecurity and fear took precedence over one's own initiatives.

It is necessary to define and understand the value line of a medical service that goes beyond the limits of any protocol and that creates the optimal dimension in which the service becomes valuable for the patient.

Question number four brings to the attention of the subjects the statement according to which the degree of development of a medical system does not necessarily generate value in the result obtained in the patient's health. The best example is provided by the health systems in Italy or the USA, which have collapsed in the fight against COVID-19 infection.

The statement was not reinforced, but neither refuted by the respondents. In general, subjects tend to believe that modernism, development, endowment are elements that are automatically reflected in the value of a medical service. The high number of deaths in countries with developed health systems has been attributed either to the mismanagement of the protocol for the hospitalization or isolation of COVID-19 cases, or to the population segment over the age of 65, much more numerous in developed countries, either due to an enormous influx of infected patients in the first phase, or due to the fact that no one is prepared to face an unknown situation. The accentuation, in the dialogue, of the idea of result in the patient's health, determined certain subjects to recognize that the value pursued by the patient in the medical care must be reflected in his health.

The second part of the question concerns the possibility of improving healthcare so that it still generates value for the patient even in extreme conditions.

Most respondents recognize the need for a change in the organizational structure and functioning of medical units, reorganization of health care, staff, its preparation, reallocation of funds, endowment of hospitals or informing the population by credible factors. Several voices stressed the need for health education of the population, which acted "out of fear", as one respondent said, even if this reaction was proved effective. The idea of intensifying prevention activity, collaboration between the medical sectors and communication between all functional levels of the system was also specified. The reformulation of the medical act and the establishment of an electronic health card that would include all the patient's medical information was another opinion. The importance of primary care and home care was not ruled out either. In the end, there were opinions in favor of establishing models borrowed from the outside, which put the patient in the center of attention of the medical service.

Conclusion: "If we want to be healthy, then we must start with prevention, not with treatment" - said one of the respondents. In general, physician 's thinking is directed towards diagnosis and treatment, and measures to improve healthcare refer to these two processes. There are certain aspects of value-based healthcare in the responses. Their need was signaled by respondents who were not physicians.

It is necessary for physicians to understand that value-based health services must demonstrate their efficiency and effectiveness (quality) in the end result obtained in the patient's health. It is necessary to

implement a communication platform between all bodies involved in the management of medical services.

The fifth question insists on approaching the clinical picture of the patient infected with the SARS-CoV-2 virus, especially in the case of comorbidities.

Almost all subjects responded in the same terms: a multidisciplinary approach. There were responses that emphasized that COVID-19 infection is a systemic disease, not a localized one, and that it is wrong to approach a patient only on a certain pathology.

Conclusion: At least at a theoretical level, the need and value of a multidisciplinary collaboration is recognized.

The sixth and seventh questions draw attention to the outcome in the patient's health, as an indicator of measuring the value of the medical service, seen through the patient's perspective.

The answers support the need to measure the value of the medical service and according to the result obtained in health, and several subjects want to specify the importance of resuming the activity in the family, society and work of the treated patient, as well as the duration of treatment and healing.

A courageous response categorizes a physician 's performance according to the patient's quality of life. A few other answers claim that the current performance indicators do not reveal the patient's satisfaction, much less the result in their health. There are also contrary answers to this statement, as well as others that support a mixture of indicators.

Conclusion: All interviewees consider it correct to introduce indicators to measure the health obtained in the patient. The value of a medical service seen through the perspective of the patient is understood differently by the medical staff.

The eighth question seeks to find out the opinion of the subjects on the change of the orientation of the medical service from a process-based to a results-based one, by introducing the measurement of the result. The answer is no, despite the fact that the need for this change is recognized, and the denial comes due to the impossibility of implementing this measure in the current policy conditions.

Conclusion: Structural and functional changes in the healthcare system are not determined by the existing evidence in reality.

It is necessary to involve political factors in implementing a profound change.

Question number nine refers to the importance of the integrated approach to the pathological condition of a patient and to the stage of its implementation in the Romanian health system.

The precarious implementation of this approach is also unanimously confirmed and there is even a statement that it will disappear from the system, because "the great integrators disappear", due to the fragmentation of medical specializations and overspecializations. The trends of medical schools in the world go on medical overspecializations. There is also the opinion that this concept is not properly understood in the medical world.

Conclusion: It is necessary to acquaint medical staff with this concept and create an organizational framework conducive to promoting such an approach if we want it to exist.

Questions ten and eleven present the integrated healthcare model based on providing a full cycle of care and the permanent presence of the multidisciplinary team. The answers to these two questions unanimously recognize the importance, the value created, the need, even the obligation to organize health care according to these processes. On the other hand, all interviewees expressed doubts about the possibility of implementation. It is interesting to note that the subjects linked these two aspects to other elements arising from integrated healthcare, such as payment by result. It is a broad aspect commented by the interviewees and mentioned as a necessity. It seems to be the subject that aroused the most interest from the interviewees (even if each considered it necessary to make certain clarifications) and which, according to the opinions issued, could lead to the practice of integrated medical care. It has also been recognized as a very good incentive for physicians and for fair competition between the public and private systems. Also, on this line, it was noted that it would be the solution for

physicians fleeing from responsibility, resorting to referrals to other specialists, which greatly complicates the healing process and increases costs.

When proposing the establishment of integrated medical practice units, several respondents expressed their agreement and even the desire to work in these units.

The answers again touched on the issue of fragmentation of healthcare, this time mentioning the rupture that exists between the weak prevention activity and the equally ignored recovery and then monitoring activity, by the rest of the care chain.

Instead, measuring the outcome at the end of the entire health care cycle elicited negative responses. Less debated was the issue of cost savings in the case of a full medical reimbursement.

Conclusion: Although it seems to be a sensitive topic, payment based on the outcome may be the link between the activities that constitute the value chain in healthcare. Although the tendency is to believe that physicians are not in a hurry to assess issues related to the economic field, no concrete opinions have been obtained on the payment of the package either from economist respondents. The tangled funding structure of the health sector raises serious barriers to a change in thinking.

There is a need for a deep justification of the assessment of the result at the end of the medical care period.

The last two questions require the opinion of the subjects about the managerial training of the management staff in the Romanian health system.

No definite answers were obtained. Some respondents finally plead for a physician with professional managerial training or for a return to the old form of management: the medical director and in his subordination the economic director.

There are, however, other types of clear statements: just a management course is not enough; a person outside the system is not suitable; a person without medical knowledge will not fully understand the needs of a patient; a physician without thorough management knowledge will be an incompetent manager. It also specifies the leadership qualities that a leader should have.

Conclusion: These last questions were the only ones on which most of the respondents could not give a concrete opinion with certainty. Most of the comments clearly show the inefficiency of the current form of management of the system, exposing incompetence or interests and goals inconsistent with the purpose of a medical system.

Discussion and conclusions

In most cases, the perception of the subjects is that the management applied to the management of health care in case of COVID-19 infection was adequate, compared to the particular conditions of our health system.

Regarding the perception of the new management model, based on integrated healthcare and its value depending on the result obtained in the patient's health, the respondents' answers are oscillating. In the context of certain questions, they are favorable to the new model, in the context of other questions they become negative.

It was found that there is a discrepancy in understanding the concept of healthcare management, between the way the theory defines it and the way it is perceived in practical reality. Therefore, the answers regarding this concept cannot be fully proven with the theoretical statements and their validity cannot be verified based on the answers.

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